

SIMULTANEOUS BUCKLING AND FUNDAMENTAL FREQUENCY OPTIMIZATION OF COMPOSITE PLATES UNDER UNCERTAIN LOADINGS

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SUMMARY

This work presents the optimization of a composite plate under uncertain loadings when buckling and fundamental frequency are taken simultaneously into account. A combination of convex modeling and minimax strategy is proposed in order to solve the optimization problem. This association reduces the strategy complexity and computational cost.

Keywords: multicriteria optimization, buckling, fundamental frequency, composite plate, uncertain loading.

INTRODUCTION

Buckling and fundamental frequency are two important design criteria in the aeronautical industry. However, most of works in this area optimizes them individually [1-4]. In some cases this can be a reasonable strategy because buckling and fundamental frequency can have similar trend. That is, an improvement on the critical load typically tends to increase the fundamental frequency. However, if the optimization is done to maximize the fundamental frequency, by the end of the process, it is necessary to check if the improvement on the fundamental frequency did not harm the buckling load and vice-versa. Aiming at overcoming this deficiency the optimization procedure proposed in this work uses a combination of convex modelling and minimax strategy to optimize buckling and fundamental frequency simultaneously.

The minimax [5] strategy as proposed here is a bilevel procedure where the criteria are maximized with respect to the design variables and minimized with respect the loading parameters. The criteria minimization with respect to the loading parameters is simplified by the fact that the minimum is located on the convex hull of the set of all initial stress states, since buckling and fundamental frequency are convex functions. The computational cost is reduced because it is necessary to check only for points on the convex hull of the load space. The criteria maximization with respect to the design variables is done by Powell's method [6].

The use of uncertain loadings makes the project closer to real situations and, consequently, more robust. The uncertain loading is defined here by uniformly distributed compressive and shear loads.

Composite plates are promising structures in the aeronautical industry. Plates are fundamental parts in aircraft manufacturing and the use of composite material is justified by the growing search for materials with high modulus per unit weight (specific modulus) and specific strength (specific strength).

Buckling and fundamental frequency are numerically computed by the finite element method [7]. The Reissner-Mindlin theory is used to describe the plate structural behavior. The plate under uniformly distributed compressive and shear loads is represented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 – Plate under mechanical loads.

PROBLEM FORMULATION

The finite element method is based on an energy principle, which states that the real equilibrium states are the ones that correspond to stationary values of total potential energy. The total potential energy functional is given in Eq. (1).

$$\pi = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{\varepsilon\}^T \{\sigma\} dV - \int_A \{f\}^T \{u\} dA \quad (1)$$

where V is the plate volume and A its area; $\{u\}$ are the displacements and $\{f\}$ are the edge tractions. The first integral in Eq. (1) is the deformation energy (U) and the second is the work of the applied loads (W).

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{\varepsilon^L\}^T [Q] \{\varepsilon^L\} dV + \frac{1}{2} \int_V \{\varepsilon^N\} \{\sigma_0\} \quad (2)$$

where the strain vector $\{\varepsilon\}$ is written in terms of a linear $\{\varepsilon^L\}$ and a nonlinear $\{\varepsilon^N\}$ strain vector, $[Q]$ is the constitutive matrix of a layer. The solution of the first and second integral in Eq. (2) yields the stiffness and geometric stiffness matrix,

respectively. $\{\sigma_0\}$ is the prebuckling stress obtained by the solution of a $[K] \{q\}_p = \{p\}$ problem. Where $[K]$ is the stiffness matrix, $\{p\}$ is the loading vector and $\{q\}_p$ is the prebuckling displacement that is used in the computation of the geometric stiffness matrix $[K_G]$. The mass matrix is obtained from the kinetic energy of the plate.

Having the stiffness, geometric stiffness and mass matrices, it is possible to formulate the buckling and fundamental frequency eigenvalue problems, given in Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively:

$$([K] - \lambda[K_G])\{q\} = \{0\} \quad (3)$$

$$([K] - \lambda[K_G] - \omega^2[M])\{q\} = \{0\} \quad (4)$$

where λ and ω are the buckling and natural frequency eigenvalues, respectively; $\{q\}$ is the vector of unknown displacements. The natural frequency modeling accounts for stress stiffening effects caused by the in-plane loading. A detailed description of the problem formulation is found in references [8, 9].

OPTIMIZATION STRATEGY

The design variable for this work is a thickness distribution that defines the plate shape. Therefore, the minimax strategy should maximize the frequency and buckling load with respect to the thickness distribution $\{t\}$ and minimize with respect to loading parameters $\{\beta\}$.

$$\max_{\{t\}} \min_{\{\beta\}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \omega(\{t\}, \{\beta\}) \\ \lambda(\{t\}, \{\beta\}) \end{array} \right\} = \max_{\{t\}} \phi(\{t\}) \quad , \quad \phi(\{t\}) = \min_{\{\beta\}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \omega(\{t\}, \{\beta\}) \\ \lambda(\{t\}, \{\beta\}) \end{array} \right\} \quad (5)$$

The first part of minimax strategy is a random search that takes advantage of the fact that buckling and natural frequency are convex functions. The functions convexity property was explained in a previous work [10]. In the first part of the procedure, a certain number of thickness distribution is randomly generated and the objective function is computed for each one. The thickness distribution that gave the best result is chosen as start point to the second part of the procedure.

The second part of minimax strategy is the objective function maximization with respect to the design variables. The maximization is done by Powell's method. The Golden Section [6] is used to solve the unidirectional optimization problem in each Powell's sub-iteration.

The function ϕ is a two-criteria objective function and it is necessary to normalized ω and λ so that they are directly comparable. The buckling load computed in this work is a nondimensional value, so it is enough to normalize only the fundamental frequency.

One way of doing this is to get frequency design requirements and use them as normalizing factors. If a fundamental frequency ω_0 is specified, then the fundamental frequency criterion used should be $\omega_i^* = \omega_i / \omega_0$. The optimal design obtained following this procedure is dependent on the design requirements. For instance, if ω_0 is set too low then the fundamental frequency criterion is expected to be unimportant since ω_i^* would be high and probably one of buckling criteria λ_i^* would be the dominant requirement.

An external loop of mass optimization can be included in the optimization strategy. This allows to remove the mass constraint and to design the structure within a desired safety factor. Figure 2 shows the optimization approach diagram.

Figure 2 – Optimization strategy.

Figure 2 shows that, if the first part of the procedure results in a buckled structure, the mass is increased and part one is repeated until a structure not buckled is obtained. This first mass optimization does not verify if the structure is under or over dimensioned according to fundamental frequency constraints and safety factors adopted. In second part of the procedure this verification is done and mass optimization external loop is performed to update (increase or decrease) mass until a minimum mass structure that meets the design requirements is obtained.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The structure chosen for the optimization is the plate represented in Fig. 1. It is a crossply laminated square plate with stacking sequence of $[(0/90)_2]_8$. The edges of the plate have dimensions $b = 0.36 \text{ m}$ and the material properties are given in Table 1.

The plate is discretized into 64 finite elements as shown in Fig. 3. Eight design variables control the thicknesses of the two outermost layers. Thicknesses t_1, t_3, t_5, t_7 are for the fourth (external) layer and t_2, t_4, t_6, t_8 are for the third layer. These thicknesses correspond to longitudinal reinforcements where elements 1 thru 8 and 57 thru 64 have thicknesses t_7 and t_8 ; elements 9 thru 16 and 49 thru 56 have thicknesses t_5 and t_6 ; elements 17 thru 24 and 41 thru 48 have thicknesses t_3 and t_4 ; finally elements 25 thru 40 have thicknesses t_1 and t_2 . The internal layers have constant thickness of 0.15 mm .

Table 1 – Material properties of T300/5208 graphite-epoxy.

Property	Value
Longitudinal modulus of elasticity, E_1 (GPa)	154.5
Transverse modulus of elasticity, E_2 (GPa)	11.13
In-plane and transverse shear modulus, G_{12} and G_{13} (GPa)	6.98
Transverse shear modulus, G_{23} (GPa)	3.36
In-plane Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.304
Density, ρ (kg/m^3)	1560

Figure 3 – Plate discretized into 64 elements.

The compressive and shear loading are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} N_x &= \beta_1 P_x \\ N_{xy} &= \beta_2 P_{xy} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where β_1 and β_2 are loading parameters, P_x and P_{xy} are the maximum magnitude expected for each individual type of loading. This work analyses three groups of load cases:

Table 2 – Load cases.

Load case	1	2	3
P_x (N/m)	2000	3200	4500
P_{xy} (N/m)	300	850	1200

The loading parameters must be bounded such that a convex hull of the loading space is identifiable. In the present simulation, the relationship imposed on the loading parameters is:

$$|\beta_1| + |\beta_2| \leq 1 \quad (7)$$

Since the fundamental frequency and stability surfaces are convex, it is sufficient to evaluate ω and λ only at the surfaces vertices. That gives the following load cases:

$$\begin{aligned} 1) \quad \beta_1 = 1 \quad \beta_2 = 0 & \quad 3) \quad \beta_1 = -1 \quad \beta_2 = 0 \\ 2) \quad \beta_1 = 0 \quad \beta_2 = 1 & \quad 4) \quad \beta_1 = 0 \quad \beta_2 = -1 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Case 1 does not cause buckle and increase the natural frequencies. Case 2 yields similar results to case 4. Therefore, only cases 3 and 4 need to be considered in the optimization procedure.

This work presents two analyses groups. In the first one it is considered a mass constraint so that $\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i = 1.2 \text{ mm}$. These results do not include the external mass optimization loop and considers load cases 1 and 2 in Table 2. The second group does not include a mass constraint and uses an external mass optimization loop. This makes possible to apply load case 3 for the loading magnitude. This work uses three frequency requirement values: $\omega_0 = 20, 40$ and 60 Hz .

Minimax optimization with mass constraint

The minimax strategy is composed of two steps. In the first step thickness values are randomly generated and the corresponding buckling and normalized frequency values

are computed. This results in two buckling and two fundamental frequency values. Among these four values the lowest is taken as the solution $\phi(\{t\})$ in Eq. (5).

The best design obtained from minimax part one is taken as the starting point to the Powell's method in part two. Powell's method is employed to find the thickness that maximizes the minimum buckling and fundamental frequency. At the end of this process the optimum thickness and the corresponding buckling and normalized fundamental frequency values are obtained. These are shown in Tables 3 and 4 for groups 1 and 2 of load cases, respectively. If the minimum among the buckling and fundamental frequency values corresponds, for example, to buckling, then it is said that buckling is the dominant criterion. The same applies for the fundamental frequency.

Table 3 – Minimax results for $N_x = 2000$ and $N_{xy} = 300$ (N/m).

	$\omega_0 = 20$ (Hz)	$\omega_0 = 40$ (Hz)	$\omega_0 = 60$ (Hz)
$\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i$	1.2	1.2	1.2
$\lambda (\beta_1=-1 \beta_2=0)$	2.701	2.344	2.344
$\omega/\omega_0 (\beta_1=-1 \beta_2=0)$	2.801	1.653	1.102
$\lambda (\beta_1=0 \beta_2=-1)$	4.940	4.529	4.529
$\omega/\omega_0 (\beta_1=0 \beta_2=-1)$	3.507	1.969	1.313

Table 3 shows that for the frequency normalization value $\omega_0 = 20$ Hz, the dominant criterion is buckling. To conclude that it was necessary to observe the thickness distribution because the λ and ω/ω_0 values are similar when $\beta_1 = -1$ and $\beta_2 = 0$. Since the optimal thickness distribution when $\omega_0 = 20$ Hz was different from when $\omega_0 = 40$ and 60 Hz (cases where frequency is the dominant criterion), it was possible to conclude that the dominant criterion is buckling.

The optimization process yields a thickness distribution capable of supporting the loading applied for the frequency normalization values $\omega_0 = 20$ e 40 Hz. However, when $\omega_0 = 20$ and 40 Hz, it is possible to say that design of the structure is over estimated and the mass optimization external loop would result a reduction of the weight of the structure. For the frequency normalization value of $\omega_0 = 60$ Hz the optimal thickness distribution satisfies the frequency requirement with 10% safety factor.

Table 4 – Minimax results for $N_x = 3200$ and $N_{xy} = 850$ (N/m).

	$\omega_0 = 20$ (Hz)	$\omega_0 = 40$ (Hz)	$\omega_0 = 60$ (Hz)
$\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i$	1.2	1.2	1.2
$\lambda (\beta_1=-1 \beta_2=0)$	1.688	1.420	1.331
$\omega/\omega_0 (\beta_1=-1 \beta_2=0)$	2.262	1.443	0.979
$\lambda (\beta_1=0 \beta_2=-1)$	1.744	1.627	1.652
$\omega/\omega_0 (\beta_1=0 \beta_2=-1)$	3.464	1.939	1.310

Analyzing the results presented in Table 4, it is possible to conclude that, when $\omega_0 = 20$ Hz the dominant criterion is buckling. When $\omega_0 = 40$ Hz the dominant criterion is frequency. However, in this case, it was also necessary to observe the thickness distribution to conclude that because λ and ω/ω_0 are too close when $\beta_1 = -1$ and $\beta_2 = 0$. When $\omega_0 = 60$ Hz and $\beta_1 = -1$ and $\beta_2 = 0$, the optimization procedure yielded $\omega/\omega_0 = 0.979$. This means that the frequency requirement was not satisfied for the considered loading. In this case, the mass optimization external loop would yield a heavier structure but capable of supporting the applied loading and meeting the frequency requirement.

The optimal laminates for buckling and fundamental frequency as dominant criteria are represented in Fig. 4 with a scaling factor of 15 along the z axis.

Figure 4 – Optimum laminates for buckling (left) and frequency (right) as dominant criterion.

Figure 4 shows that when buckling is the dominant criterion the optimum laminate mass is concentrated at the plate center, but the thicknesses for 0° and 90° layers are approximately equal. When frequency is the dominant criterion the mass is also concentrated at the plate center in just one 0° layer.

Minimax with mass optimization external loop

The minimax with mass optimization external loop was performed for loading magnitude defined by load case 3 in Table 2 and 20% safety factor. Table 5 presents the results for fundamental frequency normalization values $\omega_0 = 20, 40$ and 60 Hz.

Table 5 – Optimization strategy results for $N_x = 4500$ and $N_{xy} = 1200$ (N/m).

	$\omega_0 = 20$ (Hz)	$\omega_0 = 40$ (Hz)	$\omega_0 = 60$ (Hz)
$\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i$	1.161	1.287	1.441
λ ($\beta_1=-1$ $\beta_2=0$)	1.176	1.398	1.260
ω/ω_0 ($\beta_1=-1$ $\beta_2=0$)	1.378	1.131	1.082
λ ($\beta_1=0$ $\beta_2=-1$)	1.213	1.438	1.630
ω/ω_0 ($\beta_1=0$ $\beta_2=-1$)	2.911	1.896	1.465

Analyzing the table, it is possible to conclude that when $\omega_0 = 20 \text{ Hz}$ the dominant criterion is buckling. The thicknesses distribution necessary to satisfy this load case, with this frequency requirement, corresponds to a mass constraint of $\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i = 1.161 \text{ mm}$. When $\omega_0 = 40$ and 60 Hz the dominant criterion is frequency and the mass constraints are $\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i = 1.287 \text{ mm}$ and $\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i = 1.441 \text{ mm}$, respectively.

The minimax strategy with mass optimization external loop was used to optimize the structure subjected to group 1 of loading magnitude with $\omega_0 = 20 \text{ Hz}$. The same was done for the structure subjected to loading magnitude described by load case 2 in Table 2 for $\omega_0 = 60 \text{ Hz}$. The results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6 – Minimax with mass optimization external loop.

$N_x (N/m)$	2000	3200
$N_{xy} (N/m)$	300	850
$\omega_0 (Hz)$	20	60
$\sum_{i=1}^8 t_i$	0.780	1.259
$\lambda (\beta_1=-1 \beta_2=0)$	1.248	1.531
$\omega/\omega_0 (\beta_1=-1 \beta_2=0)$	1.176	1.018
$\lambda (\beta_1=0 \beta_2=-1)$	2.496	1.761
$\omega/\omega_0 (\beta_1=0 \beta_2=-1)$	2.624	1.332

Comparing Tables 6 and 3, it is concluded that for load case 1 and $\omega_0 = 20 \text{ Hz}$, the minimax with mass optimization external loop yielded a thickness sum 35% lower. However, with this new thickness sum, the dominant criterion is frequency.

A similar analysis can be done examining Tables 6 and 4. For load case 2 of loading magnitude and $\omega_0 = 60 \text{ Hz}$, the minimax with mass optimization external loop yielded a thickness sum 5% larger and the structure is now capable of supporting the applied loading and satisfies the frequency requirement.

The optimum laminate geometries for all these cases of minimax with mass optimization external loop are similar to the ones presented in Fig. 4. It means that when buckling is the dominant criterion the mass is concentrated on the plate center, but divided in one 0° layer and one 90° layer with similar thicknesses. When frequency is the dominant criterion the mass is concentrated on the plate center in just one 0° layer.

CONCLUSIONS

The results presented in this work are important from both the academic and practical point of views. The simultaneous optimization of buckling and fundamental frequency is a promising and little explored subject in the open literature. The use of thicknesses as design variables, in a practical sense, makes possible to establish what position is

necessary to reinforce to satisfy the requirements. However, the thicknesses found by the optimization process should be replaced by commercially available ones.

The inclusion of a mass optimization external loop is part of the efforts for making the research project more applicable to real situations. Next steps will be the inclusion of nonuniform uncertain loadings and lamination angles as design variables.

The use of the mass optimization external loop makes possible to reduce the weight of a structure with over estimated design or corrects an under estimated design so that it can sustain the loading applied and meets the design requirements.

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